

by Wiktoria Bąchorek & Monika Mynarska

Ideal number of children

We assess the ideal number of children people would like to have using the Generations and Gender Survey (GGS) data collected from 2020-2024.

Across 11 European countries, **mean personal ideal number of children ranges** from 2.09 to 2.66.

Specifically, men's ideal number of children spans from about 2.00 children in Finland to approximately 2.62 in Moldova, while women's ideals vary between 2.16 in Czechia and 2.70 in Moldova.

In most countries, **the average ideal sits just above two children;** however, Moldova stands out with reported ideals closer to three children.

In most of the observed countries, **women on average prefer having more children than men.** An opposite was found for Croatia and Czechia, and the difference was not significant in Austria.

PERSONAL IDEAL NUMBER OF CHILDREN

GGs DATA OFFERS VALUABLE INSIGHTS INTO VARIOUS FACTORS ASSOCIATED WITH CHOOSING AN IDEAL NUMBER OF CHILDREN.

Source: Generations and Gender Survey Round II – wave 1 (data from 2020-2024)